

The Role of Mental Fatigue in Soccer: A Systematic Review

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Abstract. Due to the importance of mental fatigue in the development of elite soccer players, it has been a topic of interest for researchers in the last decades. We aimed to shed light the literature published about mental fatigue in soccer in the last ten years. Secondly, based on the results obtained, we propose a new perspective on the role of cognitive effort in soccer. A systematic review (SR) was conducted following PRISMA guidelines and registered in PROSPERO. A total of 18 articles met the inclusion criteria. Results showed an increasing in the publications related to fatigue mental from 2014 onwards. The results are compared according to focus, sample, instruments and outcomes. Our proposal assumes that the physical-physiological, technical-motor and tactical-cognitive demands entail a cognitive load that reduce the performance of players. Finally, studies that prioritize controlling behavioral and physiological responses in cognitive tests are still needed.

Keywords: Training, functional performance; sport psychology; exercise; coaching.

Introduction

High-level soccer teams undertake high training and game load throughout the season (1,2). Some players play as many as 80 games in a competitive year, and also intersperse these games with practice sessions and trips that top 100,000 kilometers per season (1). The sum of these conditions has a considerable impact as, even when subjected to situations of high physical, technique, tactic and cognitive demands throughout the season, players are required to sustain high levels of individual and collective performance (3,4). These physical and technical requirements can be observed in all behaviors/movement skills performed to meet the needs of the game (i.e. sprints, jumps, runs with direction changes, technical actions, among others) and that generate significant changes in physiological responses (5). Tactical and cognitive demands, in turn, are related to the need to make a large number of tactical decisions in a time- and space-constrained environment (6,7). It can be exemplified by observing that a normal person makes about 6000 decisions throughout the day while a football player usually makes more than 2500 decisions in only 90 minutes (7). Thus, if we consider that every decision made in the game, leads to a physical and technical response of the player, as well as the realization of a tactical behavior, it is reasonable to say that the physical, technical, tactical and cognitive requirements seem to be directly associated with his performance (7,8).

It is noteworthy, however, that the need to sustain performance in the face of the number of training sessions (9), the match exigency demands and the amount of trips has raised a debate in literature on how these factors impact variables such as loss of playing quality and increased incidence of injuries (1). Overall, studies have highlighted the influence of fatigue as one of the main aspects that influence these variables (10,11). Historically, one of the traditional models used in research of exercise physiology is the Hill, Long and Lupton model in 1924 (12), called cardiovascular-catastrophic. In this model, the researchers have associate fatigue mainly with the insufficiency of the cardiovascular system to supply the oxygen demands during exercise, the production of blood lactate, and the reduced capacity for muscle contraction. This model predicts that as peripheral fatigue develops during exercise, there is a compensatory mechanism in the central nervous system that recruits additional muscle fibers that help maintain the work rate. Progressively, this process would continue until the motor units available in the muscles would be recruited, reaching a point where the work rate would fall and fatigue would manifest (12).

In contrast to the cardiovascular-catastrophic model, evidence shows that only factors associated with the ability to generate muscle contraction could not determine the regulation

of physical performance and exercise tolerance (13,14). In a long-term effort, for example, studies have shown that there is a recruitment of approximately 35-50% of the muscle fibers directly involved in the physical task (15), with this amount reaching up 60% in maximum effort conditions (16). In this way, the evidence indicates that a high physical effort is not determined by the capacity to generate muscle strength, but by the willingness to perform maximum effort (motivation) and by the way the physical task is perceived (perception of effort) (13,17). Indeed, a study conducted by Blanchfield (18) shows that motivational self-talk strategies reduce the subjective perception of effort by increasing the tolerance to physical effort in a constant load test.

Based on this evidence, the interpretation of the phenomenon of fatigue based only on variables of physical and physiological nature reduces the possibility of a deeper understanding of the impact of this phenomenon on the performance of soccer players, leaving some points to be clarified (19–22). Thus, there is another strand of studies on fatigue that start to take into account aspects of human cognition (20). Supported by scientific evidence in the fields of neuroscience and sports psychology, this strand has considered the impact of a phenomenon known as mental fatigue (19). Mental fatigue can be conceptualized as a sensation experienced during or after a prolonged period of cognitive activity, characterized by feeling tired and lack of energy (19,23). This phenomenon has a direct implication on the performance of soccer players, as it influences aspects such as perceived exertion, perception of physical tiredness and even the risk of injury (24–26).

Martin and collaborators (27) claim that the deleterious effect of mental fatigue is associated with adenosine accumulation in the brain. In this sense, cognitive activity that occurs in brain regions associated with more complex mental processes is impaired by adenosine accumulation and reduction of surrounding glucose. This temporary shortage of glucose and increased adenosine levels obstruct the release of neurotransmitters such as dopamine (27, 28). The result is an increase in effort perception and a decrease in motivation and level of engagement in the activities undertaken and, consequently, reduced performance (27).

Based on the aforementioned evidence, investigations into the state of mental fatigue in football have suggested that when the player reaches this state there is a significant loss of performance (e.g., physical, technical, tactical, cognitive) (11, 29). However, there are still points to be clarified about what happens before the player reaches the state of mental fatigue. One of the hypotheses about what leads players to a state of mental fatigue may be associated with issues related to the cognitive load imposed by the activity and, consequently, the

cognitive effort invested acutely (demands that arise throughout games and training) or chronically (demands that arise throughout the season) (30, 31). When not properly controlled, these factors seem to reduce the recovery process and favor the player to go into a state of mental fatigue, causing a greater number of errors in decision making, decreased performance, and risk of injury (32).

Furthermore, in soccer, the increase in competitiveness increases the cognitive load that must be managed by the players in each game and training. This requires that these players substantially increase the cognitive effort investment in an attempt to maintain their performance levels (6, 30), for example, their eye movements. Thus, the probability of the soccer player going into a state of mental fatigue increases due to a high cognitive effort investment during the game or throughout the season (22, 33). Recent investigations that sought to understand the impact of mental fatigue, reported evidence regarding the negative effects of this phenomenon on the physical (5, 34); technical (34, 35); tactical (11, 36) and cognitive (20) aspects of soccer performance. Studies have also shown that mentally fatigued players are less coupled with their group and with the task goals (36), in addition to displaying reduced levels of motivation and enthusiasm (37), increased difficulties in expressing emotions (37), reduced level of discipline (38) and significant loss in concentration and in the ability to focus their attention on relevant details (38).

The studies highlighted above provide enough evidence on the negative impact of mental fatigue on soccer players. However, it is worth mentioning that the theoretical background regarding the influence of mental fatigue on soccer performance is recent and has been substantially developed over the last 10 years and based on the psychobiological model (28). This model considers that the conscious regulation (decision making) of the exercise rhythm is determined by motivation and, above all, by the subjective perception of effort (19, 39, 40). However, there are still some doubts about the use of this model to explain the phenomenon of mental fatigue in the context of soccer, in addition to other points to be considered, understood and evaluated on this phenomenon, such as the influence of cognitive effort on the occurrence of the state of mental fatigue. Although mental fatigue cannot be characterized as a subjective state, it can be assessed subjectively with visual analogue scales (34, 59), and objectively through Global Positioning System (36) or Mobile Eye Tracking (30), for instance. Nevertheless, its effects and results are objective, for instance, increasing the adenosine concentration, mentioned before in the introduction. Thus, the present review aims to describe the currently available evidence in the literature about the influence of mental

fatigue in soccer, as well as to discuss the possibilities for future investigations and interventions.

Methods

Search limits

An exhaustive and systematic search of five scientific literature databases (Web of Science-All Databases, Scopus, PubMed, SPORTDiscus, ERIC-Ebsco, and Academic Search Ultimate) was conducted. On the one hand, these databases were selected because they included articles published in journals indexed in the Journal Citation Report (JCR) or a similar index (e.g., the Scimago Journal Rank-SJR). On the other hand, a systematic search was conducted to obtain an extended examination of the phenomenon under study. The Figure 1 shows the search strategy used in each database or journal.

[Insert table 1 near here]

The search was conducted following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews (SR) and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (41), including the PICO strategy: Participants, Intervention, Comparators and Outcomes (see Table 2). The search finished September 27th, 2021.

[Insert table 2 near here]

Selection criteria

Articles were included based on the following criteria: (a) studies published in peer-reviewed international journals indexed in JCR or SJR databases; (b) studies published from 2009 to 2019 (both inclusive); (c) studies that included quantitative and/or qualitative methods and findings; (d) articles that focused on mental fatigue in soccer players, and (e) studies published in English or Spanish.

As exclusion criteria, we decided not to include those articles (a) not indexed in JCR/SJR databases; (b) conducted on other sports/contexts different from soccer/football/futsal; (c) articles with not enough data to complete the table results; and (d) articles focused on neuromuscular fatigue or subjective perception of fatigue, but not on mental fatigue. The Figure 1 shows the number of articles excluded by these reasons.

We decided to include both quantitative and qualitative articles in the SR for two reasons. On the one hand, the sample of the review would be too small if we removed the qualitative ones, due to this line of investigation does not count with many articles published. On the other hand, both quantitative and qualitative research can play a role in research synthesis (42), maximising the strengths of both approaches and increasing the relevance of SR (43). Although calls have been made previously to further use and explore mixed-methods reviews in a systematic process, these methods are still not commonly utilised, or have little awareness surrounding them (44). Thus, due to there are no SR previous which consider both designs (qualitative and quantitative) on this topic, we decided to include them for this review, with the purpose to add new knowledge to this field.

In short, a qualitative synthesis might be used to explore the findings of a prior quantitative synthesis or vice versa (45). Duplicated documents were disqualified at the first level of exclusion. At the second level of exclusion, documents were selected according to year of publication, title and abstract. Finally, at the third level of exclusion, the selected articles were fully read and some disregarded for the final analysis. The systematic search process and the number of results can be found in Figure 1, following the indications of PRISMA (46).

[Insert figure 1 near here]

Both the systematic search process and the number of results are shown in Figure 1. Subsequent to the elimination of many articles at the first level of exclusion, 5,899 original articles were retrieved as potential studies to be included in the review. A total of five articles were included in the sample from the references lists of other articles. Then, 4730 were discarded at the second level of exclusion. Finally, after reading the full text of 134 articles, 18 were included in this study.

Data extraction and reliability

After the initial search, the articles that did not fit the date of publication were discarded at the first level of exclusion. The articles that met the selection criteria were retrieved for this review. In order to obtain relevant information, the following categories were used (47): authors; location; objectives; sample size; method; data sources; and results. Mendeley was used to collect the documents from all the databases and filter the results.

The first and the second author did the screening and the data extraction processes. They screened all the articles at first and second exclusion level separately. Then, they meet to check the articles selected for each one. They reach an agreement about the doubtful articles.

Quality assessment and level of evidence

First, the quality of the review process was assessed and included in the PROSPERO register. It is an international database of prospectively registered SR in health and social care, welfare, public health, education, crime, justice, and international development. Key features of the review protocol are recorded and maintained as a permanent record. It allows researchers to comply with PRISMA, providing a public record of their planned methods and raising awareness of their review, as well as allowing comparison of manuscript findings.

Second, the quality of this SR was also assessed using the PRISMA guidelines (46). This evaluation tool includes an evidence-based set of items to report the quality of SR and meta-analysis.

Third, the criteria for assessing the quality of the selected studies were based on the Checklist for Measuring Study Quality (e.g., is the hypothesis/aim of the study clearly described? (48)), the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies statement (e.g., is it possible to use the design in other studies? (49)), and the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials statement (e.g., the study's blinding and quality assessment (50)).

Fourth, previous studies (51–53) were used to obtain a quality score for each investigation based on the following criteria: (a) programme description; (b) JCR/SJR journal; (c) detailed methodological description; (d) sample or number of participants; and (e) length of the implementation. Each item was scored from '0' to '2' using the criteria described in Table 2. A total quality score from all the selected publications was calculated by adding up the number of positive items between '0' and '10'. Investigations were classified as: (a) low quality: a score lower than '3'; (b) moderate quality: a score between '4' and '6'; and (c) high quality: a score of '7' or higher. Two experts on Physical Education performed this evaluation independently. The two experts along with the second author met before the assessment to clarify how to decide between all the options (e.g., how to decide between a 'brief undetailed description' and a 'detailed description'). Some articles not included in this SR were taken as examples to discuss the assessment criteria. When the two experts reached an agreement in all the criteria, they were prepared to begin the evaluation of all the articles separately. The selection criteria to be an expert were: (1) to have published articles in top indexed journals

(JCR) in the last 5 years, (2) to have participated in SR, (3) to have, at least, one master degree in Physical Education and Sport, and (4) to have an minimum experience of five years as a researcher. Cronbach's alpha (0.95) indicated high reliability among the individual evaluations (51). After that, the second author met with the two experts to reach an agreement in those articles in which they did not agree.

[Insert table 3 near here]

Results

First, the evolution of publications about mental fatigue is shown in Figure 2. Here, it is possible to observe how the number of publications in the last ten years is increasingly, from 2 publication in the years 2009-2010 to ten publications in the last 3 years.

[Insert figure 2 near here]

Table 3 shows the 18 studies conducted around the world in the last ten years. The most important and relevant information from each study was assessed following the structure used in previous SR (52): 'author(s)' (and publication year); 'focus'; 'sample description'; 'analysis/data sources'; and 'outcomes'.

Discussion

This paper aims to describe the currently available evidence in the literature about the influence of mental fatigue in soccer, as well as to discuss the possibilities for future investigations and interventions, considering cognitive effort as an intervening variable to mental fatigue and its detrimental effects on the performance of soccer players. In general, it is possible to highlight a growing interest in this topic over the last 10 years. Such interest is related to the fact that research systematically indicates a negative effect of mental fatigue on sports performance of soccer players, leading to physical (3, 5, 34), technical (34, 35, 54), tactical (11, 36) and cognitive damage (20, 55, 56).

Due to these impairments, researchers are increasingly focused on building knowledge about the influence of mental fatigue on soccer players, as well as on identifying forms of intervention that minimize its effects (11, 29). However, it is noteworthy that there is still a low amount of evidence in the specialized literature that seeks to evaluate the influence of

cognitive effort on soccer players, as well as its impact on the onset of a state of mental fatigue (30). Apparently, this is due to the difficulty in evaluating and controlling this variable during practice sessions and games. In short, based on the content up until this point, it appears that research efforts may have been undermined by a number of different terms that are used interchangeably without clear definition or theoretical stance (30). Below are some of the main points of the papers selected for this review and some future perspectives for the studies on cognitive effort and mental fatigue in soccer.

Focus

Regarding the focus of the papers selected for this review, it is possible to observe that 17 out of 18 articles examined the effects of mental fatigue on the performance of soccer players and only one (1) study investigated the influence of cognitive effort on soccer players.

It is also noteworthy that there was a change in the direction of the selected papers over the years. The first studies on this subject published between 2009 and 2015 sought to substantially address intervening aspects of mental fatigue and its responses at the cognitive (24, 57, 58) and physical levels (5). These studies can be considered as the first evidence that cognitive fatigue results in impaired performance by soccer players. Subsequently, from 2016, the focus has been on performing experimental work, aiming to induce players to a state of mental fatigue. In this scenario, players participated in previously defined laboratory tasks (using tests such as the Stoop test) lasting from 20 to 40 minutes to induce players to a state of mental fatigue. Subsequently, the players performed an experimental task to evaluate their performance. Thus, players were evaluated in two situations: a control (i. e. without mental fatigue induction) and an experimental one (i. e. with mental fatigue induction), in order to examine how mental fatigue affects the performance of soccer players (11, 20, 21, 36,54–56, 59–61).

With respect to cognitive effort, a recent study conducted by Cardoso and colleagues (28) provided a different approach by removing the fatigue induction task (fixed load) and using pupillometry to assess the level of cognitive effort during a soccer-specific video task. This paper aimed to identify the association between cognitive effort and the number of players' tactical knowledge. The evidence from this study allowed us to identify pupillary behavior as a physiological marker conducive to the assessment of cognitive effort in soccer, opening up an important reflection on the control of this variable in the training context, before the player undertakes a state of mental fatigue.

Sample description

The samples of the selected articles are heterogeneous, which allows us to infer that the effects of cognitive effort and state of mental fatigue affect different populations of soccer players. In this review, it was observed that from the 16 selected experimental articles, 15 evaluated male soccer players and only one (1) study evaluated female players. It is worth mentioning that this study was performed in futsal (60). Nine (9) of the selected studies evaluated soccer players competing at the highest competitive levels, participating in the 1st, 2nd, or 3rd division of the national championships; five (5) studies evaluated young soccer players and two (2) studies evaluated semi-professional players. Two (2) of the selected studies are literature reviews and did not account for the description of the samples of the present study.

Instruments and data resources and analysis

As for the main instruments and data analyzed presented in the selected articles, the following stand out: 1) instruments and metrics regarding mental fatigue induction tasks, 2) instruments and metrics of subjective scales of mental fatigue and physical effort evaluation, 3) instruments and metrics for the assessment of cognitive effort (e. g. pupillometry and pupillary behavior) and 4) instruments and metrics for the assessment of tactical, technical, physical and cognitive performance.

Regarding the mental fatigue induction tasks, different tasks were used, especially the paper (34, 61, 62) and computer versions of the Stroop test (11, 54). These tests lasted between 20 and 40 minutes. The Stroop test requires attention and inhibition of automatic response, being a task that potentially induces mental fatigue when used over a long period (11). Although not an ecological task, the Stroop test requires relevant and necessary cognitive skills for soccer performance, namely: selective and sustained attention, and inhibitory control (11). In the practice of soccer, selective and sustained attention allows the active processing of information from the enormous amount of information available during the game (63). In view of the information available in the environment, the ability of players to inhibit automatic responses, initiated actions or behavior deemed inappropriate, or competing distracting stimuli that may compromise performance is considered important (6).

In an attempt to find more ecological task, it is worth mentioning the use of a 20-minute coordinating/mental task (36). Concomitantly to the mental fatigue induction task, some

studies have gathered information on heart rate, number of response errors and stimulus-response time, in order to identify the level of engagement and attention on tasks (34, 61, 62).

Regarding the use of subjective scales to assess the state of mental fatigue, we highlight the use of the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) to measure the level of mental fatigue, mental effort, and motivation, the BRUMS questionnaire to evaluate the measures of fatigue, NASA-TLX for workload assessment and the scale proposed (61) to measure motivation (20, 35, 36, 54, 61). To assess the perceived exertion index on the physical task, the studies used the Borg Scale (34) and its adapted version - CR-10 (34, 36, 62).

For the assessment of cognitive effort, the use of the pupillometry technique during a specific video task in soccer is highlighted. This technique takes into account that players who require less cognitive effort (i.e., less pupil dilation) to make decisions on specific tasks are less likely to undertake a state of mental fatigue compared to players who require a greater cognitive effort for making decisions (30).

Finally, regarding the instruments and equipment for performance evaluation, it is worth highlighting the use of heart rate measurements for physiological measurements (34, 54). As for physical measurements, evaluations of total distance traveled, vertical jump, sprint velocities, among others were used (34). It is noteworthy that in recent studies the use of GPS has been considered as an important resource for the evaluation of physical variables in competitive contexts (Coutinho et al., 2017, 2018). For evaluation of technical performance, the articles have used the Loughborough Soccer Passing and Shooting Test - LSPT and LSST to evaluate passing and kicking efficiency (34), evaluations through small-sided games (54, 62) and specific passing tasks (35). With respect to tactical performance, studies have used the System of Tactical Assessment in Soccer - FUT-SAT to evaluate player's tactical efficiency based on the core principles of soccer (11, 30), in addition to the assessment of the teams' collective behavior through small-sided games (36, 62). Finally, for cognitive performance, studies have used video tests to evaluate decision making. (20) and other laboratory tests that provide cognitive skills measurements (55, 60).

It should be noted that the data analyzed and the metrics generated from the aforementioned instruments and equipment have been very useful in enlightening the influence of cognitive effort and mental fatigue on the performance of soccer players.

Outcomes

Most investigations on mental fatigue and cognitive effort in the literature point to the influence of these variables on players' performance. In the present review, considering only soccer players, it is evident that in a state of mental fatigue players show a significant decrease in performance. In this scenario, we highlight studies that evaluated the influence of mental fatigue and cognitive effort on the performance of players in the different dimensions, namely: two (2) studies that evaluated the influence on physical performance, one (1) study on technical performance, seven (7) studies on cognitive performance and, seven (7) studies that evaluated more than one dimension of the game in the same paper. The subdivisions considering the game's divisions: physical, technical, tactical and cognitive, were designed to make the understanding of the impact of cognitive effort and mental fatigue on the players' performance more didactic. We highlight below the main findings for each of the dimensions of the game.

Regarding the effects of mental fatigue on physical performance, it can be observed that when mentally fatigued, players show a reduction in the total distance and lower average speed in stages that comprised lower speeds, such as walking and running at low intensity (5, 21). Note that these studies did not observe changes in players' physiological responses (34), albeit changes in subjective responses were observed (e.g., perceived exertion indices). These results confirm that subjective measures are important indicators to identify mental fatigue in soccer and that increased subjective perception of effort reduces physical performance. However, it is noteworthy that the interpretations for these results are centered on the psychobiological model (19). In this model, it is assumed that the conscious regulation (decision making) of the exercise rhythm is determined by the motivation and the perception of the effort (17). These assumptions are distinct from those traditionally prioritized by exercise physiology, in which fatigue is understood as a process with an exclusive neuromuscular and metabolic origin, associated with a physiological marker (19). These issues highlighted above deserve further exploration since; when assessing physical responses in reduced game situations, an opposite response to the results reported above is observed. Thompson and colleagues (64) conducted an study with English academy soccer players, concluding that mental fatigue is experienced as a result of match-play, remaining 24 hours post-match.

Results have shown that there is an increase in the number of physical actions in repeated sprints (51) and the distance traveled at higher speeds (Kunrath et al., 2018). These findings seem to occur because the dynamic nature of small-sided games allows players with

greater freedom to adjust their efforts and change the pace of the game (51), as players can adapt their behaviors since they are not pushed to the maximum of their exercise tolerance. Thus, although there is a tendency for higher perceived exertion indices in subjective responses after mental fatigue (36, 54), the assumptions of the psychobiological model do not seem to fully meet the specificity of the soccer game. Despite the prevailing aerobic metabolic and endurance demands of the game, the frequent decision-making situations are based on problems about field occupancy and management of the playing space rather than in the effort itself, as recommended by the psychobiological model (40).

Regarding the technical performance, the studies evaluated the effects of mental fatigue particularly on passing and kicking skills (35, 54, 61). In general, in a state of mental fatigue, passing tasks result in a higher number of penalties for errors, lower accuracy of perfect passes, and more errors in targets (35). As for the kicking test, in a state of mental fatigue, there was a decrease in kicking accuracy and the ball speed in goal attempts (34). By testing the hypothesis that mental fatigue would have negative effects on technical performance in small-sided games, Badin and colleagues (51) observed that players displayed a decrease in the quality of technical actions such as ball possession and tackles. According to Smith (21), it is assumed that technical performance was impaired in mental fatigue due to a reduction in the amount of attention allocated to the task.

As for cognitive performance, it was observed, above all, a significant influence of the state of mental fatigue and cognitive effort on aspects related to players' decision making, perception, attentional levels and tactical knowledge about the game. For example, Smith (20) found negative effects of mental fatigue on decision-making time and accuracy. It is likely that the impairment of cognitive skills, such as the decrease in attentional levels (65) and in the efficiency of information processing (66), may have influenced players' decision making (34). The results of this study also show the impacts of mental fatigue on players' visual search, causing negative effects on decision-making time and accuracy. In attempting to identify a way to reduce the deleterious effects of mental fatigue on soccer players' decision making, Cardoso and colleagues (30) demonstrated that tactical knowledge about the game is a factor that favors the player to make decisions employing less cognitive effort, reducing their chance of undertaking a state of mental fatigue.

Finally, with respect to the tactical dimension, it is observed that the effects of mental fatigue negatively influence the tactical responses at the collective and individual levels. At the collective level, it is possible to notice lower lateral synchronization, dispersion and contraction

velocity of the team in 6 vs. 6 small-sided games (36). At the individual level, Kunrath and collaborators (11) demonstrate that in a state of mental fatigue actions related to the core tactical principles of balance and defensive unity are impaired.

The results of studies on cognitive effort and mental fatigue reinforce the need for greater control of these variables to reduce their negative effects on players' performance. Thus, it is important to monitor cognitive effort during tasks (e.g., training, matches, travels, etc.) in order to avoid achieving a state of mental fatigue (67). However, when the player undertakes a state of mental fatigue, speeding up recovery to reduce its effects becomes a necessary action.

Proposal for an association between cognitive effort and mental fatigue, future work guidelines

In order to guide research on this subject, investing in the understanding of mechanisms related to mental fatigue and its negative influence on the performance of soccer players is recommended. For this purpose, it is important to highlight that, the mechanism proposed by Smith and colleagues (22) clarify important aspects related to mental fatigue. In this paper, the author describes the stimulus that contribute for the player to enter a state of mental fatigue, the mechanisms involved, and the outcomes deficiencies caused by it in soccer. However, studies that prioritize controlling behavioral and physiological responses in cognitive tests are still needed.

This is due to the fact that most studies still have difficulty systematizing and indicating how the tasks performed (whether in vivo or in situ) are associated with the characteristics (individual and collective) of the players and lead to the onset of mental fatigue. This fact makes it difficult to control and evaluate the process of recovery from mental fatigue and even to prevent its occurrence. Given these difficulties, we deem necessary a research avenue to assist in the process of control and evaluation of this variable in the context of soccer.

Therefore, the management of the cognitive load and the evaluation and control of the cognitive effort are important aspects to be considered in training, in games, and during the recovery process of players. However, more studies are needed to identify the real associations between the state of mental fatigue, cognitive effort, and its influences on the performance of soccer players. Besides, further studies should be conducted to identify the main forms of measurement for the control and evaluation of cognitive effort/mental fatigue state in the context of soccer.

It is expected that following this direction will result in a substantial progress in the control and evaluation of the stages that precede the onset of mental fatigue in soccer (i.e., cognitive load and cognitive effort) in order to maximize the control of these variables and avoid that players get into a state of mental fatigue and consequently have their performances harmed.

References

1. Bengtsson H, Ekstrand J, Waldén M, Hägglund M. Muscle injury rate in professional football is higher in matches played within 5 days since the previous match: a 14-year prospective study with more than 130 000 match observations. *Br J Sports Med* [Internet]. 2018 Sep [cited 2019 Dec 22];52(17):1116–22. Available from: <https://bjsm.bmj.com/content/52/17/1116.abstract>
2. Job R, Dalziel J. Defining fatigue as a condition of the organism and distinguishing it from habituation, adaptation, and boredom. In: Hancock PA, editor. *Stress, workload, and fatigue*. Mahwah, NJ, US: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers; 2001.
3. Smith MR, Thompson C, Marcora SM, Skorski S, Meyer T, Coutts AJ. Mental Fatigue and Soccer: Current Knowledge and Future Directions. *Sport Med*. 2018 Jul;48(7):1525–32.
4. Le Mansec Y, Pageaux B, Nordez A, Dorel S, Jubeau M. Mental fatigue alters the speed and the accuracy of the ball in table tennis. *J Sports Sci* [Internet]. 2018 Dec 2;36(23):2751–9. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02640414.2017.1418647>
5. Hogarth LW, Burkett BJ, McKean MR. Neuromuscular and Perceptual Fatigue Responses to Consecutive Tag Football Matches. *Int J Sports Physiol Perform* [Internet]. 2015 Jul;10(5):559–65. Available from: <https://journals.humankinetics.com/view/journals/ijsp/10/5/article-p559.xml>
6. Vickers JN, Williams AM. The Role of Mental Processes in Elite Sports Performance. *Oxford Res Encycl Psychol*. 2017;(1):1–25.
7. Teoldo I, Guilherme J, Garganta J. Training football for smart playing: On tactical performance of teams and players. Curitiba: Appris; 2017. 319 p.
8. García-Calvo T, Pulido JJ, Ponce-Bordón JC, López-Gajardo MÁ, Teoldo Costa I, Díaz-García J. Can Rules in Technical-Tactical Decisions Influence on Physical and Mental Load during Soccer Training? A Pilot Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* [Internet].

- 2021 Apr 19;18(8):4313. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/8/4313>
9. Russell S, Jenkins DG, Halson SL, Juliff LE, Kelly VG. How do elite female team sport athletes experience mental fatigue? Comparison between international competition, training and preparation camps. *Eur J Sport Sci* [Internet]. 2021 Mar 25;1–11. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17461391.2021.1897165>
 10. Zemková E, Hamar D. The effect of soccer match induced fatigue on neuromuscular performance. *Kinesiology*. 2009;41(2):195–202.
 11. Kunrath CA, Cardoso F, Nakamura FY, Teoldo I. Mental fatigue as a conditioner of the tactical and physical response in soccer players: a pilot study. *Hum Mov*. 2018;19(3):16–22.
 12. Hill A V, Long CHN, Lupton H. Muscular exercise, lactic acid and the supply and utilization of oxygen. *Proc R Soc*. 1924;97:155–76.
 13. Marcora S, Staiano W. The limit to exercise tolerance in humans: Mind over muscle? *Eur J Appl Physiol*. 2010;109(4):763–70.
 14. Noakes TD. Time to move beyond a brainless exercise physiology: the evidence for complex regulation of human exercise performance. *Appl Physiol Nutr Metab*. 2011;36:23–35.
 15. Amann M, Eldridge MW, Lovering AT, Stickland MK, Pegelow DF, Dempsey JA. Arterial oxygenation influences central motor output and exercise performance via effects on peripheral locomotor muscle fatigue in humans. *J Physiol*. 2006;575(3):937–52.
 16. Sloniger MA, Cureton KJ, Prior BM, Evans EM. Lower extremity muscle activation during horizontal and uphill running. *J Appl Physiol*. 1997;83(6):2073–9.
 17. Van Cutsem J, Marcora S, De Pauw K, Bailey S, Meeusen R, Roelands B. The effects of mental fatigue on physical performance: a systematic review. *Sport Med*. 2017;47(8):1569–88.
 18. Blanchfield AW, Hardy J, De Morree HM, Staiano W, Marcora SM. Talking yourself out of exhaustion: the effects of self-talk on endurance performance. *Med Sci Sport Exerc*. 2014;46(5):998–1007.
 19. Marcora SM, Staiano W, Manning V. Mental fatigue impairs physical performance in humans. *J Appl Physiol* [Internet]. 2009 Mar [cited 2021 Jun 23];106(3):857–64. Available from: <https://www.physiology.org/doi/10.1152/jappphysiol.91324.2008>
 20. Smith MR, Zeuwts L, Lenoir M, Hens N, De Jong LMS, Coutts AJ. Mental fatigue

- impairs soccer-specific decision-making skill. *J Sports Sci* [Internet]. 2016 Jul 17;34(14):1297–304. Available from: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02640414.2016.1156241>
21. Smith M, Coutts A, Merlini M, Deprez D, Lenoir M, Marcora S. Mental Fatigue Impairs Soccer-Specific Physical and Technical Performance. *Med Sci Sport Exerc* [Internet]. 2016 Feb;48(2):267–76. Available from: <https://journals.lww.com/00005768-201602000-00012>
 22. Smith MR, Thompson C, Marcora SM, Skorski S, Meyer T, Coutts AJ. Mental Fatigue and Soccer: Current Knowledge and Future Directions. *Sport Med* [Internet]. 2018 Jul 5;48(7):1525–32. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s40279-018-0908-2>
 23. Boksem MAS, Tops M. Mental fatigue: Costs and benefits. *Brain Res Rev* [Internet]. 2008 Nov;59(1):125–39. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0165017308000714>
 24. Thompson CJ, Franssen J, Skorski S, Smith MR, Meyer T, Barrett S, et al. Mental Fatigue in Football: Is it Time to Shift the Goalposts? An Evaluation of the Current Methodology. *Sport Med*. 2019;49(2):177–83.
 25. Nédélec M, McCall A, Carling C, Legall F, Berthoin S, Dupont G. Recovery in Soccer. *Sport Med*. 2013 Jan;43(12):997–1015.
 26. Nozaki S, Tanaka M, Mizuno K, Ataka S, Mizuma H, Tahara T, et al. Mental and physical fatigue-related biochemical alterations. *Nutrition* [Internet]. 2009 Jan;25(1):51–7. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S089990070800316X>
 27. Martin K, Meeusen R, Thompson KG, Keegan R, Rattray B. Mental Fatigue Impairs Endurance Performance: A Physiological Explanation. *Sport Med* [Internet]. 2018 Sep 19;48(9):2041–51. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s40279-018-0946-9>
 28. Pageaux B, Lepers R, Dietz KC, Marcora SM. Response inhibition impairs subsequent self-paced endurance performance. *Eur J Appl Physiol* [Internet]. 2014 May 15;114(5):1095–105. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00421-014-2838-5>
 29. Kunrath C, Cardoso F, García T, Da Costa I. Mental fatigue in soccer: a systematic review. *Rev Bras Med do Esporte*. 2020;26(2):172–8.
 30. Cardoso F da SL, González-Villora S, Guilherme J, Teoldo I. Young Soccer Players

- With Higher Tactical Knowledge Display Lower Cognitive Effort. Percept Mot Skills [Internet]. 2019 Feb 11 [cited 2019 Feb 19]; Available from: <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0031512519826437>
31. Benoit C-E, Solopchuk O, Borragán G, Carbonnelle A, Van Durme S, Zénon A. Cognitive task avoidance correlates with fatigue-induced performance decrement but not with subjective fatigue. *Neuropsychologia* [Internet]. 2019 Feb [cited 2019 Dec 22];123:30–40. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0028393218302896>
 32. Smith MR, Thompson C, Marcora SM, Skorski S, Meyer T, Coutts AJ. Mental Fatigue and Soccer: Current Knowledge and Future Directions. *Sport Med*. 2018 Jul;48(7):1525–32.
 33. Thompson CJ, Fransén J, Skorski S, Smith MR, Meyer T, Barrett S, et al. Mental Fatigue in Football: Is it Time to Shift the Goalposts? An Evaluation of the Current Methodology. *Sport Med* [Internet]. 2019 Feb 2 [cited 2021 Jun 23];49(2):177–83. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-018-1016-z>
 34. Smith MR, Coutts AJ, Merlini M, Deprez D, Lenoir M, Marcora SM. Mental Fatigue Impairs Soccer-Specific Physical and Technical Performance. *Med Sci Sport Exerc* [Internet]. 2016 Feb;48(2):267–76. Available from: <https://journals.lww.com/00005768-201602000-00012>
 35. Alarcón F, Castillo-Díaz A, Madinabeitia I, Castillo-Rodríguez A, Cárdenas D. La carga mental deteriora la precisión del pase en jugadores de fútbol. *Rev Psicol del Deport*. 2018 Jul;27(2):155–64.
 36. Coutinho D, Gonçalves B, Travassos B, Wong DP, Coutts AJ, Sampaio JE. Mental Fatigue and Spatial References Impair Soccer Players' Physical and Tactical Performances. *Front Psychol* [Internet]. 2017 Sep 21 [cited 2019 Dec 22];8(SEP). Available from: <http://journal.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01645/full>
 37. Schiphof-Godart L, Roelands B, Hettinga FJ. Drive in Sports: How Mental Fatigue Affects Endurance Performance. *Front Psychol* [Internet]. 2018 Aug 17;9. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01383/full>
 38. Russell S, Jenkins D, Smith M, Halson S, Kelly V. The application of mental fatigue research to elite team sport performance: New perspectives. *J Sci Med Sport*. 2019 Jun;22(6):723–8.
 39. Kunrath CA, Nakamura FY, Roca A, Tessitore A, Teoldo I. How does mental fatigue

- affect soccer performance during small-sided games? A cognitive, tactical and physical approach. *J Sport Sci.* 2020;in press.
40. Pageaux B. The Psychobiological Model of Endurance Performance: An Effort-Based Decision-Making Theory to Explain Self-Paced Endurance Performance. *Sport Med* [Internet]. 2014 Sep 9;44(9):1319–20. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s40279-014-0198-2>
 41. Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement. *PLoS Med* [Internet]. 2009 Jul 21;6(7):e1000097. Available from: <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000097>
 42. Cooper H, Hedges L, Valentine J. The handbook of research synthesis and meta-analysis [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2021 Jun 23]. Available from: https://books.google.es/books?hl=es&lr=&id=tfexDwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=Cooper+2017+both+quantitative+and+qualitative+research+can+play+a+role+in+research+synthesis&ots=RMnAjr4M1W&sig=M8bD3i_cIEfRi4tnO3z2mm_hEKI
 43. Harden A, Thomas J. Mixed methods and systematic reviews: Examples and emerging issues. In: Tashakkori A, Teddie C, editors. *SAGE Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social & Behavioral Research* [Internet]. 2010 [cited 2021 Jun 23]. Available from: <https://methods.sagepub.com/base/download/BookChapter/sage-handbook-of-mixed-methods-social-behavioral-research-2e/n29.xml>
 44. Pearson A, White H, Bath-Hextall F, Salmond S, Apostolo J, Kirkpatrick P. A mixed-methods approach to systematic reviews. *Int J Evid Based Healthc* [Internet]. 2015 [cited 2021 Jun 23];13(3):121–31. Available from: https://journals.lww.com/ijebh/fulltext/2015/09000/A_mixed_methods_approach_to_systematic_reviews.3.aspx
 45. Pluye P, Hong QN. Combining the Power of Stories and the Power of Numbers: Mixed Methods Research and Mixed Studies Reviews. *Annu Rev Public Health* [Internet]. 2014 Mar 18 [cited 2021 Jun 23];35(1):29–45. Available from: <http://www.annualreviews.org/doi/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-032013-182440>
 46. Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement. *PLoS Med.* 2009 Jul;6(7):e1000097.
 47. Harris JD, Quatman CE, Manring MM, Siston RA, Flanigan DC. How to Write a Systematic Review. *Am J Sports Med* [Internet]. 2014 Nov 7 [cited 2021 Jun

- 23];42(11):2761–8. Available from: <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0363546513497567>
48. Downs SH, Black N. The feasibility of creating a checklist for the assessment of the methodological quality both of randomised and non-randomised studies of health care interventions. *J Epidemiol Community Heal* [Internet]. 1998 Jun 1 [cited 2021 Jun 23];52(6):377–84. Available from: <http://jech.bmj.com/>
 49. von Elm E, Altman DG, Egger M, Pocock SJ, Gøtzsche PC, Vandenbroucke JP. The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) Statement: Guidelines for Reporting Observational Studies. *Ann Intern Med* [Internet]. 2007 Oct 16 [cited 2021 Jun 23];147(8):573. Available from: <http://annals.org/article.aspx?doi=10.7326/0003-4819-147-8-200710160-00010>
 50. Moher D, Schulz KF, Altman DG. The CONSORT statement: revised recommendations for improving the quality of reports of parallel-group randomised trials. *Clin Oral Investig* [Internet]. 2003 Mar 31 [cited 2021 Jun 23];7(1):2–7. Available from: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00784-002-0188-x>
 51. Araújo R, Mesquita I, Hastie P. Review of the status of learning in research on sport education: Future research and practice. *J Sports Sci Med* [Internet]. 2014 [cited 2021 Jun 23];13(4):846–58. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4234955/>
 52. Lun T, Chu A, Zhang T. Motivational processes in Sport Education programs among high school students: A systematic review. *Eur Phys Educ Rev* [Internet]. 2018 Aug 1 [cited 2021 Jun 23];24(3):372–94. Available from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1356336X17751231>
 53. Hastie PA, Casey A. Fidelity in Models-Based Practice Research in Sport Pedagogy: A Guide for Future Investigations. *J Teach Phys Educ* [Internet]. 2014 Jul [cited 2019 Feb 6];33(3):422–31. Available from: <http://journals.humankinetics.com/doi/10.1123/jtpe.2013-0141>
 54. Badin OO, Smith MR, Conte D, Coutts AJ. Mental Fatigue: Impairment of Technical Performance in Small-Sided Soccer Games. *Int J Sports Physiol Perform* [Internet]. 2016 Nov [cited 2019 Dec 22];11(8):1100–5. Available from: <https://journals.humankinetics.com/view/journals/ijsp/11/8/article-p1100.xml>
 55. Gantois P, Caputo Ferreira ME, Lima-Junior D de, Nakamura FY, Batista GR, Fonseca FS, et al. Effects of mental fatigue on passing decision-making performance in

- professional soccer athletes. *Eur J Sport Sci* [Internet]. 2020 Apr 20;20(4):534–43. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17461391.2019.1656781>
56. Pullinger SA, Bradley PS, Causer J, Ford PR, Newlove A, Patel K, et al. Football-induced fatigue in hypoxia impairs repeated sprint ability and perceptual-cognitive skills. *Sci Med Footb* [Internet]. 2019 Jul 3;3(3):221–30. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/24733938.2019.1591633>
 57. Clemente Suárez VJ, Muñoz VE, Martínez A. Fatiga del sistema nervioso después de realizar un test de capacidad de sprints repetidos (RSA) en jugadores de fútbol de categoría juvenil. *Apunt Med l'Esport* [Internet]. 2011 Oct;46(172):177–82. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1886658111000247>
 58. de la Vega R, Almeida M, Ruiz R, Miranda M, del Valle S. Entrenamiento atencional aplicado en condiciones de fatiga en fútbol. *Rev Int Med Y Ciencias La Act Fis Y Del Deport*. 2011;11(42):384–406.
 59. Alarcón F, Castillo-Díaz A, Madinabeitia I, Castillo-Rodríguez A, Cárdenas D. La carga mental deteriora la precisión del pase en jugadores de fútbol. *J Sport Psychol* [Internet]. 2018 [cited 2018 Oct 5];(2):155–64. Available from: <http://rua.ua.es/dspace/handle/10045/78307>
 60. Sepahvand H, Pirzad Jahromi G, Sahraei H, Meftahi GH. Studying the Perceptive and Cognitive Function Under the Stress of Match in Female Futsal Players. *Asian J Sports Med*. 2017 Sep;In Press(In Press).
 61. Smith MR, Fransen J, Deprez D, Lenoir M, Coutts AJ. Impact of mental fatigue on speed and accuracy components of soccer-specific skills. *Sci Med Footb* [Internet]. 2017 Jan 2;1(1):48–52. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02640414.2016.1252850>
 62. Coutinho D, Gonçalves B, Wong DP, Travassos B, Coutts AJ, Sampaio J. Exploring the effects of mental and muscular fatigue in soccer players' performance. *Hum Mov Sci* [Internet]. 2018 Apr;58(October 2017):287–96. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0167945717307790>
 63. Faubert J. Professional athletes have extraordinary skills for rapidly learning complex and neutral dynamic visual scenes. *Sci Rep*. 2013;3(1):1154.
 64. Thompson CJ, Noon M, Towlson C, Perry J, Coutts AJ, Harper LD, et al. Understanding the presence of mental fatigue in English academy soccer players. *J Sports Sci*. 2020 Jul

- 2;38(13):1524–30.
65. Boksem MAS, Meijman TF, Lorist MM. Mental fatigue, motivation and action monitoring. *Biol Psychol* [Internet]. 2006 May [cited 2019 Dec 22];72(2):123–32. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301051105001481>
 66. van der Linden D, Frese M, Meijman TF. Mental fatigue and the control of cognitive processes: effects on perseveration and planning. *Acta Psychol (Amst)* [Internet]. 2003 May;113(1):45–65. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0001691802001506>
 67. Calleja-Gonzalez J, Marques-Jimenez D, Jones M, Huyghe T, Navarro F, Delextrat A, et al. What are we doing wrong when athletes report higher levels of fatigue from traveling than from training or competition? *Front Psychol*. 2020 Feb;11.